

PECULIARITIES OF INTERNATIONAL WORDS TRANSLATION

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The article discusses foreign words and peculiarities in translating them. In the modern world, the majority of linguists observe an astounding increase in the evolution of many language kinds. Every word, even those that sprang on their own, has a backstory. The most brilliant aspect of language is its vocabulary, which has connections to every aspect of human civilization, including politics, sports, technology, science, and the arts. This is because words are generated in these domains to facilitate communication, which is essential to human activity. Knowledge of their origins is a valuable resource for the development of technical terminology. Greatest number of English words, including foreign words, are ambiguous and have several meanings. This is especially true with technical terms, where words can have multiple meanings depending on the context. International words that are the consequence of linguistic borrowing make up the research's material.

Key words: international, lexis, borrowing, internationalization, peculiarity, specify.

The article's goal is to examine foreign words and determine appropriate translation strategies for cross-cultural communication. In order to meet the predetermined goals, it is necessary to investigate the meaning of the phrase "international word" or "internationalism," as well as the ways in which these concepts have permeated other languages and the specifics of the English to Russian translation of international words. Scientific terminology is the research's source material. The phenomenon of internationalization is evident in terminology, as there is a continuous rise in the quantity of words from other languages. The internationalization of terminology aids in the growth of language. It is evident that internationalism is a category of interlanguage that emerges solely through language comparisons.

Corresponding the "Dictionary of linguistic terms" written by O.Akhmanova, an international term or phrase is one that is shared by multiple languages or bears resemblance to its historical evolution. An international word is a term that has been borrowed by most languages in the globe and started to be used by other languages.

The scientific and technical revolutions have expedited the development of internationalization in public life. As society has evolved in terms of economics,

society, and culture, the need for studying international vocabulary has been reinforced. The subject of internationalism in linguistics has never been less important, particularly in light of the growing significance of international words in a variety of linguistic contexts related to language contact and comparison processes.

We can choose a set of terms known as internationalisms from among the enormous number of borrowed words in any language. A unique occurrence among the many kinds of cross-linguistic groups on the planet is internationalization. These kinds of indicators greatly facilitate linguistic communication and are crucial to information sharing procedures. Furthermore, the most obvious and well-known example of global commonality in language dictionaries is the international lexicon. The reason that internationalism has played a vital role in the evolution of modern languages is because these languages are widely accepted as lexical-semantic expressions of the most significant ideas in contemporary society. Without a doubt, its significance lies in breaking down language barriers through translation and language training as well as in the development of an international second language. The concept of internationalism unites words that function in various, first of all unrelated languages, and that coincide by their outward form, subject to the regular correspondence of sounds and graphical units in certain languages, with fully or partially coinciding sense, expressing the concept of the international nature from the field of science and technology, politics and culture, and art. International words are defined as those that involve two or more countries, are made up of individuals or groups from multiple countries, are active or well-known throughout several countries, according to Merriam-Webster's Learner's Dictionary.

Greek and Latin loanwords make up the majority of the international vocabulary in European languages. For instance, the terms thesis, hypothesis, theory, crisis, lexicon, atom, autonomy, automatic, democracy, philosophy, dialectic, thesis, synthesis, analysis, nation, republic, matter, nature, principle, federation, progress, university, faculty, subject, object, liberal, and radical are all of Latin origin, as is much of the vocabulary. The field of specific terminology used in various branches of research and technology is mostly associated with international words. In the fields of physics, chemistry, and medicine, some examples include atom, proton, radio, diode, detector, and focus; mathematics, plus, integral, and theorem; and influenza, virus, and syndrome. International vocabulary, according to D. Rozental, derives from Latin words "inter" meaning

"between" and "nation" (nationis) meaning "people." International words are terms that share a common etymology and are found in many languages. They are typically produced according to the phonetic and morphological rules of the language.

The issue of translating foreign words is one of the most significant ones nowadays, but sadly, not much research has been done on it. In addition to the many pseudo-internationalisms that can bewilder even highly skilled translators and entirely misinterpret the meaning of the statement, translators also face challenges when deciding between upholding international form and selecting non-single-rooted equivalents in their mother tongue or another language. When words from other countries have synonyms, an issue occurs. The international word in this instance has a more terminologically scientific quality, and the decision between the two synonyms will rely on the text's purpose and readership. When working with this type of language, an interpreter may encounter several typical errors. Here are some tips for avoiding these errors. The goal of the research is to determine which translation of the international vocabulary is best.

Technical and scientific writings can be translated with the "false friends" problem, which has its own unique characteristics. In the scientific and technical literature, it is possible to observe that the translator's "false friends" have particular characteristics. This specificity is shown in the qualities of "false friends" as well as in their quantitative makeup. Given that a sizable portion of the terms in the translator's "false friends" category are regarded as foreign terms. When it comes to the quantitative specificity of the translator's "false friends" in scientific and technical literature, the word "accurate" is a "classic" example; it also has another meaning, "точный.". Additional instances can be found in S.M. Varinov's lexicon : "figure" - "цифра, ілястрація, креслення", not only "фігура", "party" - "вечірка, свято", not only "комфорт"; "director" - "голова, режисер", not only "директор", just "партія", "suitable pressure" - "правильний вибор тиснення", адекватне тиснення; "Candidate Fumer Compositions" - "Кандидатные газообразующие составы, "представляющие интерес газообразующие составы; "optimal delivery date"; "теоретическая гарантийная дата выпуска продукции"; "идеальная гарантийная дата"; "is merely slightly bigger" – только маргинально больше лишь немного больше; "massive tube failures" - сильные повреждения труб массивованных разрушения; "permanent change" refers to the non-opportunistic reversal of a gradient; "laboratory control plays a critical part" – критическую роль играет

лабораторный контроль, важная роль играет контроль, "Criteria failure" – a proof of the object's disintegration "control criterion": управления и регулирования критерий, "Column failure" refers to the depletion of soil organic matter, while "contamination failure" refers to the accumulation of waste products; "device operating failure" - отказ в процессе устройства работы.

The examples demonstrate how a literal translation is erroneous and leads to semantic distortions. Numerous global terms related to science, such as analysis, contender, scenario, crucial, original, history, pioneer, and revolutionary scientific and technical writings frequently contain terms like "practical," "signal," "traditional," etc., which serve as "false translators' friends." These English terms are easily recognized in the translation since they have equivalents in Russian and Ukrainian that relate to their global relevance. These identifications either distort the content of the speech or violate target language stylistic conventions. Concerning international terminology, the meanings of terms such as "reactor," "proton," "electron," and "resonance" are frequently the same across languages. The amount of meaning is where the differences lie. Semantic content is significantly described in cases of general scientific parallel internationalisms. The majority of typical scientific internationalisms used in English are unclear. Internationalism has a broader range of values than languages like Russian or Ukrainian.

There are three basic conversions when translating words from other languages that have a natural character. These are the de-specialization in translation and the specialization of English common scientific international words. Lexis specialization is the replacement of the proper word in the original language, which has a more precise general meaning, in place of the popular English word. A common equivalent is the outcome of translation specialization. These counterparts provide the meaning of the relevant English terms as they are expressed in the local language's scientific lexicon. For instance, "the power of the approach" - «достоинство подхода», the source of unreliability - «источник ненадежности», the entire realm of biological structures - «вся совокупность биологических структур»; the aforementioned insights are primarily derived from... - «приведенные выше выводы получены главным образом на основании...»; the main draw of the active filter - «основное достоинство активного фильтра»; these vehicles are equipped with a radar sensor system - «эти автомобили оборудованы радиолокационной системой». These instances highlight how common words in scientific

translation have specialized meanings. De-specialization is demonstrated by the replacement of Russian non-international vocabulary with common scientific English terms. These scientific words are not involved in the procedure. For example, “era” – “период”, “phase – “фаза»; apalitical– «расчетный», «теоретический»). It may cause the original information to be distorted.

Therefore, the presence of an international Lexis and, more importantly, an understanding of its operational parameters and system-structural linkages can aid in the optimization of cognitive processes across all domains of human endeavor. Many worldwide linguists think of lexis as a historical artifact and as a phenomenon inherent in language. We cannot, however, claim that there is a wealth of information on internationalism among the books currently in print on linguistics, lexicography, theory, and translation practice. It is imperative to confirm that information on internationalism-related topics is supplied consistently. It provides the groundwork for more in-depth study of this subject.

References:

1. Akulenko V.V. (1972), Issues of internationalization of language lexis. Kharkiv, Ukraine: [in Russian].
2. Ahmanova O.S. (2004), Glossary of linguistic terms. Moscow, Russia: [in Russian].
3. Barinov S.M. (1991). Big English-Russian Polytechnic Dictionary. Moscow, Russia: [in Russian].
4. Belchikov Y.A. (1959), International terminology in the Russian language. Moscow, Russia: [in Russian].
5. Borisova L.I. (2005), False Translator’s friends. Moscow, Russia: [in Russian].
6. Vinogradov S.N. (1993), Vagueness of terminology and its causes (based on the material of word formation terminology. Novgorod, Russia: [in Russian].
7. Zhluktenko Y.A. (1980), International elements in lexicon and terminology. Kiev, Ukraine: [in Ukrainian].
8. Rozental D.E. (1976), Dictionary of linguistic terms: A Handbook for Teachers. Moscow, Russia: [in Russian].
9. Rozental D.E. (1976), Dictionary of linguistic terms. http://www.gumer.info/bibliotek_Buks/Linguist/DicTermin/j.php [in English].